

LEARNING SOUND WAVES' EFFECTS ON EMG SIGNALS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE*Ozuomba Uzoma Divinelove Moses**MD, MSc, and PhD in view. Georgian Technical University, Georgia
Gurtskaia Z.**MD, PhD, Professor. Georgian Technical University***Abstract**

Sound is an energy (Raghu, 2018; Choi, Jung, & Kang, 2019) or a vibration that can be propagated into human bodies as sound waves and these sound waves have either positive or negative effects on both physical and mental well-being of people (Bass & Clark, 2003; World Health Organization, 2018; Reybrouck, Podlipniak, & Welch, 2019). These positive or negative sound wave effects can culminate into therapeutic or pathologic effects hence our aim of creating an artificial intelligence-based model for detection and prediction of therapeutic sound frequencies and amplitudes based on individual health needs. Our research aims to design an artificial intelligence-based (AI) model for detecting human muscle response to different sound frequencies and amplitudes. Using artificial intelligence, we were able to find the difference between the EMG signals recorded from the volunteers during different sound waves applications. This means that human muscle responds to different sound signals and react differently.

Keywords: Sound waves, sound therapy, sound healing, sound frequency generator, Frequency, Amplitude, 432 Hz, 440 Hz, 880 Hz, 1320 Hz, 30 dB, 60 dB, 90 dB, complex tone, harmonic overtones, octave, CleveLab kit, machine learning, Matlab.

INTRODUCTION

Sound wave is equally described by their frequencies and amplitudes (Katz, Clavijo, Rizk, & Ramasamy, 2019). The frequency range within which human adults can detect and hear sounds is from 20 Hz to 20,000 Hz (20 Hz to 20 kHz) unlike in human infants where the frequency is slightly higher than 20 kHz, and as these infants grow, they lose some high frequency sensitivities (Naz & Friedman, 2020; Luengrungrus, Thanawirattananit, & Teeramatwanich, 2024; Prell, Spankovich, Lobarinas, & Griffiths, 2014). Sound amplitude level at or less than 70 dB in twenty four hour time period per year is safe in humans (Fink, 2017), and humans can safely listen to sound amplitude level of 80 dB for a time length of 40 hours per week but if the sound amplitude level is 90 dB, the safety level decreases to only four hours per week (WHO, 2024); furthermore, exposure to amplitude of 80 dB poses no risk in many people but 85 dB poses minor health risks while 90 dB and above poses significant health risks such as hearing loss (Lutman, 2000).

Frequency 440 Hz was declared a standard tuning pitch or reference frequency that musical instruments are tuned to in 1939 (Gribenski, 2023; Piilonen, 2024). In spite of this declaration, some scientists and theorists still prefer frequency 432 Hz due to its therapeutic effects of being more satisfying to volunteered subjects inducing focus in them, manages their anxiety and stress better, and slightly reduced their mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mean heart rate and mean respiratory values than sound frequency 440 Hz (Calamassi & Pomponi, 2019; Calamassi, et al., 2022). And while frequencies 880 Hz and 1320 Hz are both harmonic overtones of fundamental tone "A" 440 Hz

by virtues of being multiples of this fundamental tone (Franken, 2024), 880 Hz in particular is not only an octave higher than 440 Hz (Chasin, 2014; StackExchange, 2016), it is also a musical note A5 that when applied on humans plays detoxification roles, enhances circulation and stimulates immune defense mechanisms against infections thereby aiding lung and general body wound healing (Tucker, 2025). Apart from being multiples of the fundamental frequency 440 Hz, (Fishman, Micheyl, & Steinschneider, 2013), frequencies 880 Hz and 1320 Hz in conflation with this same 440 Hz are called complex tone.

AIM: Our research aims to design an artificial intelligence-based (AI) model for detecting human muscle response to different sound frequencies and amplitudes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Healthy volunteers underwent Electromyography (EMG) studies in a room with silence and sound waves of various frequencies and amplitudes. For EMG data collection, we used the CleveLab system with five snap electrodes, the Sound Frequency Generator app with an inbuilt Amplitude meter, and an Amplifier. The CleveLab system allows us to obtain data in both graphical and numerical form. To build the AI model, we used numerical data.

Electrodes connected to each volunteer's elbow bone and the bicep and wrist extensor muscles. Records were done during silence (3 times) and using four different frequencies: 432 Hz, 440 Hz, 880 Hz, 1320 Hz each with three different amplitudes: 30 dB, 60 dB, 90 dB. (Table 1). The duration of the records was 5 seconds.

Table 1.

Frequency (Hz)	432			440			880			1320		
Amplitude (dB)	30	60	90	30	60	90	30	60	90	30	60	90

Each record contained graphical and numerical EMG data. A healthcare professional examined the

graphical data to find differences between EMG graphical records. The machine learning model was built using Matlab software. As we had labelled data, we used the classification method with Matlab Tools—Classification Learner. After preprocessing the data we trained the model using different statistical methods.

RESULT:

After recording the data during silence and after using different frequencies and amplitudes we collected numeric and graphical data. No difference was found

by healthcare professional between graphical EMG data.

After we build the AI model using numeric data and trained it with the different statistical methods. Different models showed different accuracy. Best results were achieved with the **Subspace KNN** with Learner type: **Nearest neighbors** (72 %).

The model can better recognize the muscle EMG signal when it is recorded in silence (100%) and muscle response to the 880 HZ signal with different amplitude (100%).

Figure 1. True positive and False positive rates.

Figure 2. True positive and False Negative rates.

CONCLUSION:

Using artificial intelligence, it is possible to reveal hidden information that is often impossible even for professionals. Our research has shown that it is impossible even for a healthcare professional to detect regularities between EMG images recorded during exposure

to different sound frequencies since such changes are minimal. Using artificial intelligence, we were able to find the difference between these signals. This means that human muscle responds to different sound signals and react differently. The response to 880 Hz was incredibly higher.

Muscle tissue is a vital part of the heart, blood vessels, and digestive system. Muscular system broadly comprises smooth, cardiac and skeletal muscles and it plays vital roles in energy metabolism, vision, organ protection, immunity, endocrine and reproductive activities, cardiovascular and respiratory activities, posture, mobility, stability, regulation of body temperature and homeostasis. Owing to all these vital roles of human muscle, and ultimately its responses and different reactions to different sound signals, we are highly of the opinion that more attention needs to be paid to the impact of sound signals on human health.

References

1. Bass, A. H., & Clark, C. W. (2003). *The Physical Acoustic of Underwater Sound Communication*. Retrieved from Springer Handbook of Auditory Research DOI https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-22762-8_2: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/0-387-22762-8_2
2. Calamassi, D., & Pomponi, G. P. (2019). Music Tuned to 440 Hz Versus 432 Hz and the Health Effects: A Double-blind Cross-over Pilot Study. *PubMed PMID: 31031095 DOI: 10.1016/j.explore.2019.04.001*.
3. Calamassi, D., Vigni, M. L., Fumagalli, C., Gheri, F., Pomponi, G. P., & Bambi, S. (2022). Listening to music tuned to 440 hz versus 432 hz to reduce anxiety and stress in emergency nurses during the Covid-19 pandemic: a double-blind, randomized controlled pilot study. *PMC PubMed Central PMID: PMC9534204 PMID: 35545982 doi: 10.23750/abm.v93iS2.12915*.
4. Chasin, M. (2014, July 22). *The Importance of 1.059 in Music (and Audiology)*. Retrieved from hearingreview: <https://hearingreview.com/practice-building/practice-management/continuing-education/importance-1-059-music-audiology>
5. Choi, J., Jung, I., & Kang, C.-Y. (2019). A brief review of sound energy harvesting. *ScienceDirect https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.11.036*.
6. Fink, D. J. (2017). What Is a Safe Noise Level for the Public? *PMC PubMed Central PMID: PMC5308171 PMID: 27925831 editorial Am J Public Health. 2017 Jan;107(1):44-45. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2016.303527*.
7. Fishman, Y. I., Micheyl, C., & Steinschneider, M. (2013). Neural Representation of Harmonic Complex Tones in Primary Auditory Cortex of the Awake Monkey. *PMC PubMed Central PMID3685833 PMID: 23785145 J Neurosci. 2013 Jun 19;33(25):10312-10323. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0020-13.2013*.
8. Franken, E. (2024, November 6). *Overtones and undertones in guitar sound*. Retrieved from chickenpicks: <https://www.chickenpicks.com/overtones-and-undertones-in-guitar-sound/?srsltid=AfmBOoqCBRA2XH1mcFKRzOPRe5AHUcryqOWPArmm2XwI4gFiNLmkwHG>
9. Gribenski, F. (2023). Tuning the World The Rise of 440 Hertz in Music, Science, and Politics, 1859–1955. *The University of Chicago Press*.
10. Katz, J. E., Clavijo, R. I., Rizk, P., & Ramasamy, R. (2019). The Basic Physics of Waves, Soundwaves, and Shockwaves for Erectile Dysfunction. *PMC PubMed Central doi: 10.1016/j.sxmr.2019.09.004*.
11. Luengrungrus, K., Thanawirattananit, P., & Teeramatwanich, W. (2024). Normative Data of Extended High Frequency Audiometry in Normal Hearing Subjects with Different Aged Groups. *PubMed PMID: 39727612 PMID: PMC11674001 DOI: 10.3390/audiolres14060089*.
12. Lutman, M. E. (2000). What is the risk of noise-induced hearing loss at 80, 85, 90 dB(A) and above? *PubMed PMID: 10912379 DOI: 10.1093/ocmed/50.4.274*.
13. Naz, S., & Friedman, T. B. (2020). Growth factor and receptor malfunctions associated with human genetic deafness. *PubMed Epub 2019 Oct 23. PMID: 31506927 PMID: PMC8232520 DOI: 10.1111/cge.13641*.
14. Piilonen, M. (2024). Tuning the World: The Rise of 440 Hertz in Music, Science, and Politics (1859–1955). *ResearchGate Journal of Music Theory 68(1):194-199 DOI:10.1215/00222909-10974848*.
15. Prell, C. L., Spankovich, C., Lobarinas, E., & Griffiths, S. K. (2014). Extended High Frequency Thresholds in College Students: Effects of Recreational Noise. *PMC PubMed Central doi: 10.3766/jaaa.24.8.9*.
16. Raghu, M. (2018). A Study to Explore the Effects of Sound Vibrations on Consciousness. *Horizontal Research Publishing Corporation DOI: 10.13189/ijrh.2018.060302*.
17. Reybrouck, M., Podlipniak, P., & Welch, D. (2019). Music and Noise: Same or Different? What Our Body Tells Us. *PMC PubMed Central doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01153*.
18. StackExchange. (2016, April 7). *A (440 Hz) and A (880 Hz) are completely different sounds to me. Does this mean I'm tone deaf?* Retrieved from Music Practice and Theory: <https://music.stackexchange.com/questions/43335/a-440-hz-and-a-880-hz-are-completely-different-sounds-to-me-does-this-mean>
19. Tucker, M. (2025, January 22). *880 Hz for Healing Complete Guide*. Retrieved from Altered Mind Waves: <https://alteredmindwaves.com/880-hz-complete-guide/>
20. WHO. (2024, May 29). *Deafness and hearing loss: Safe listening*. Retrieved from who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers: <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/deafness-and-hearing-loss-safe-listening>
21. World Health Organization. (2018). *Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European region - Executive Summary*. WHO Regional Office for Europe UN City, Marmorvej 51 DK-2100 Copenhagen Ø, Denmark: World Health Organization Document number: WHO/EURO:2018-3287-43046-60243 WHO-EURO-2018-3287-43046-60243-eng.